
INFLUENCE OF WORKPLACE LEISURE ACTIVITIES ON EMPLOYEE PRODUCTIVITY IN OIL AND GAS ENTERPRISES PORTHARCOURT, IN RIVERS STATE, NIGERIA.

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Abstract: *The study explored the influence of workplace leisure activities on employee productivity in oil and gas enterprises in Port Harcourt Rivers State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study determines the effect of availability of workplace leisure activities on employees' commitment. The study further ascertain the effect of work life balance on employee job satisfaction in oil and gas in PortHacourt Rivers State, Nigeria.. Descriptive survey research design was adopted to collect data from the respondents with the aid a structured questionnaire. Arithmetic mean was used to analyse respondents' responses and the hypotheses were tested using Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient and the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS, version 27). Hypothesis one revealed that there is a statistically significant positive effect of availability of workplace leisure on workforce commitment. Workplace leisure activities therefore have a substantial positive relationship ($r = 0.882$, $n = 203$, p value of 0.001 ($p < 0.05$)). There is also a substantial positive relationship ($r = 0.801$, $n = 203$, p value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$)) between work life balance and employee job satisfaction in Oil and Gas enterprises in PortHarcourt Rivers State, Nigeria. The study concludes that there is statistically significant positive relationship between Workplace leisure and employee productivity in Oil and Gas enterprises in PortHarcourt Rivers State, Nigeria. Based on the conclusion, the study recommended that oil and Gas enterprises should make available work leisure in their work place which improves the workforce commitment in other to achieve greater productivity. Oil and gas companies should put in place well-planned, structured leisure programs that meet the various demands of their staff. Fitness courses, leisure sports, and team-building activities which in turn improves the physical, social, and creative activities that these programs ought to provide.*

Keywords: *Workplace, Leisure, Activities, Employee, Productivity, Workforce Commitment, employee job satisfaction and work life balance.*

Introduction

Organizations play a major role in work-leisure of their employees. Leisure can help employees to relieve stress, restore energy, and enhance performance at work (Cheng, Chang and Lien, 2020). Workplace leisure has grown in importance as a component of organizational development initiatives, especially in high-demand industries like the oil and gas sector. Recreational activities provide a break that can help prevent burnout and increase overall productivity in oil and gas companies, where workers frequently deal with long hours, physically demanding duties, and high levels of stress. Empirical evidence indicates that integrating leisure pursuits like team sports, recreational initiatives, and relaxation methods can notably improve worker productivity by providing opportunities for mental and physical rejuvenation (Cho, 2024). Businesses that provide organized leisure time also witness increases in productivity and attention as their workers come back to work with renewed energy and enthusiasm. Recreational activities at work also foster an atmosphere that is conducive to creativity and innovation, which helps workers solve difficult problems and think more clearly (Kekeocha, Anoke, Chukwuemeka-Onuzulike and Nzewi, 2023). Apart from their influence on output, recreational pursuits are essential for promoting employee loyalty in oil and gas companies. These companies, especially in Rivers State, Nigeria, have significant difficulties keeping employees because of the high stress and safety hazards associated with their line of work.

Employees who participate in leisure activities offered by their employers are more likely to feel appreciated and supported, which strengthens their emotional bond with the company, claim (Babatope, Okoye, Adekunle and Fejoh, 2023). When workers believe their well-being is being emphasized they are less inclined to look for work elsewhere, which in turn strengthens organizational commitment. Additionally, team building and a sense of belonging are fostered by group recreational activities, and these are crucial elements of employee loyalty. An organization's overall stability is eventually enhanced by a culture that incorporates work-life balance through leisure activities, as this leads to higher job satisfaction and less intent to leave (Olanipekun and Olanipekun, 2024). When recreational activities are deliberately implemented to increase employee dedication and productivity, the oil and gas industry in Rivers State stands to gain a great deal. Because they work in high-stress conditions all the time, employees in this industry may perform poorly and have significant turnover rates if their mental and physical health is not addressed. Employee motivation, job happiness, and loyalty frequently rise when businesses incorporate leisure into their work environments (Nwibere, 2024).

Firms can build a more resilient workforce by incorporating leisure activities into their larger HRM strategy. Sheyindemi, Daniel and Abubakar, (2023) posits that leisure in work place will ensure that employees are not only dedicated to the company's objectives but also routinely perform at higher levels because leisure activities provide a boost to morale and rejuvenation. As a result, recreational pursuits are a vital component of Rivers State's oil and gas companies' long-term profitability.

Ingbedion, (2024), state that workplace leisure initiatives like fitness classes, social events, and get-togethers are becoming more popular as a way to encourage work-life balance and foster a more laid-back and encouraging work atmosphere. Studies indicate that workers who engage in recreational pursuits on a regular basis tend to have reduced stress levels, enhanced physical and mental health, and increased well-being—all of which are associated with increased productivity (Nnani, Okonkwo and Orga, 2024). Furthermore, leisure time activities can increase organizational commitment and a sense of belonging, which can lower turnover intentions and improve job satisfaction (Ojobu, Ezeh and Joe-Akunne, 2024). Even though the advantages of leisure time are well known, less is known about how they affect certain industries, like oil and gas, especially in Nigeria's Rivers State (Nwabali and Elenwo, 2024).

Rivers State, home to several international and local businesses, is a major center for Nigeria's oil and gas sector. Given the demanding nature of the sector, it is imperative to investigate the potential of recreational pursuits to improve employee outcomes in this particular area (Omosebi, 2024). In oil and gas companies in Rivers State, Nigeria, this study aims to look into the impact of recreational activities on worker engagement and productivity. This research attempts to offer insights that can guide human resource strategies and help to better organizational performance by looking at the kinds and availability of leisure activities in these organizations and their relationship with employee outcomes. This research is essential and timely given the particular issues encountered by workers in the oil and gas industry. It aims to close a gap in the literature by presenting actual data on the beneficial effects of leisure activities on labor dedication and productivity in this demanding business. Achama and Amah, (2024) are of the opinion that companies in Rivers State and elsewhere will benefit from an understanding of these factors as they create successful leisure initiatives that raise employee satisfaction and boost overall company success.

Statement of the Problem

Workers in the oil and gas sector, especially in Nigeria's Rivers State, frequently face long workweeks, physically tasking jobs, and high-stress work situations, all of which can be detrimental to their general well-being and productivity. Many businesses in this industry struggle to maintain a consistently productive and engaged staff, despite the fact that employee performance and workforce commitment are critical to preserving competitive advantage. The oil and gas industry's long hours and high levels of pressure can cause burnout, weariness, and high turnover rates, all of which compromise the sustainability and efficiency of the company. The benefits of recreational activities for enhancing worker well-being and job performance have been the subject of numerous studies; however, little is known about how much of an impact these activities have on worker commitment and productivity in the context of the oil and gas industry, particularly in Nigeria.

To further aggravate the negative effects of job stress and strengthen organizational commitment, a large number of Rivers State oil and gas companies lack organized leisure programs. Firms risk

missing out on possibilities to increase employee productivity, contentment, and retention if they do not have a comprehensive knowledge of the role that leisure activities play in this sector. Given the sector's vital role in Nigeria's economy and the industry's increasing competitiveness, this knowledge gap is especially alarming. Accordingly, it is imperative to look into how bringing recreational activities into the workplace could help with these problems and improve employee outcomes like loyalty, job happiness, and productivity.

This study aims to investigate the influence of recreational activities at work on worker commitment and productivity in Rivers State oil and gas firms. Through an analysis of the direct and indirect effects of these activities on workers' performance and loyalty to their companies, this research attempts to offer insightful information about how to successfully incorporate leisure into oil and gas companies' corporate cultures in order to enhance overall organizational effectiveness.

Objectives of the Study

The primary objective of this study is to explore the relationship between the influence of leisure activities on employee productivity in oil and gas firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. To achieve this broad objective, the study will focus on the following specific objectives:

1. To examine the relationship between workplace leisure activities and workforce commitment in oil and gas enterprises in Port Harcourt Rivers State, Nigeria.
2. To determine the relationship between work life balance and employee job satisfaction in oil and gas enterprises in Port Harcourt Rivers State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were designed to guide the investigation:

1. What is the relationship between workplace leisure activities and workforce commitment in oil and gas enterprises in Port Harcourt Rivers State, Nigeria?
2. Is there any relationship between work life balance and employee job satisfaction in oil and gas enterprises in Port Harcourt Rivers State, Nigeria.

Research Hypotheses

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between the availability of workplace leisure activities and workforce commitment in oil and gas enterprises in Port Harcourt Rivers State, Nigeria.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between work life balance and employee job satisfaction in oil and gas enterprises in Port Harcourt Rivers State, Nigeria.

Significance of the Study

Stakeholder involved in the oil and gas sector: many people, especially in Nigeria's Rivers State, will find great value in this study. Ultimately, knowing how recreational activities affect worker dedication and productivity can help oil and gas companies improve their workforce management strategies. For policymakers and industry regulators, the study provides evidence of the importance of investing in employee well-being as a critical component of industry sustainability and growth. Thus, the study not

only addresses immediate organizational needs but also contributes to broader discussions on improving labor conditions and promoting sustainable industry practices. Again, the insights that will be gained from this research can inform human resource policies and practices not only within the oil and gas sector but also in other high-demand sectors facing similar challenges. By providing empirical evidence on the benefits of leisure activities, the study will support broader discussions on the integration of work-life balance initiatives into organizational cultures, promoting a shift towards more holistic approaches to employee management.

Scope of the Study

The scope of this study focuses on how leisure activities, specifically inside oil and gas enterprises in Rivers State, Nigeria, influence worker commitment and productivity. The study is confined to oil and gas firms operating in Rivers State, Nigeria. This region is selected due to its significant role in the oil and gas sector and the specific challenges faced by firms in this area, including high-stress work environments and issues related to employee productivity and commitment.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Leisure Activities in the Workplace

Leisure activities refer to recreational or relaxation-oriented activities that employees engage in during their work or break times. These activities can range from physical exercise, sports, and recreational games to creative pursuits, social events, and relaxation techniques (Gellmers and Yan, 2023). The integration of leisure activities into the workplace is based on the premise that such activities can enhance overall employee well-being, reduce stress, and contribute to a more positive work environment (Igwebuike and Onyezere, 2023). Work-life balance, employee wellbeing, and a more engaged and productive workforce are the three main goals of incorporating leisure into the workplace. Leisure activities are becoming more and more recognized in today's workplaces for their ability to improve employee morale, lower stress levels, and increase overall productivity. Research indicates that giving workers time to relax and rejuvenate helps them come back to work with more vigor and concentration, which enhances productivity (Obiora-Okafo and Onodugo, 2021).

Leisure time activities can also help employees connect with one another and build a greater sense of community and teamwork. This can lower turnover rates and increase organizational commitment (Enefifa and Akintokunbo, 2020). Additionally, these activities serve as protective measures against the physical and mental exhaustion that frequently results from hard work environments, especially in high-stress industries like the oil and gas industry. Balogun, (2023) state that it is possible to customize leisure activities to fit the unique requirements and organizational culture. For example, businesses in physically demanding sectors like the oil and gas industry might give priority to physical wellness initiatives to assist staff in coping with the physical demands of their work. Organizations with more sedentary job descriptions, on the other hand, might concentrate on stress-relieving exercises like

creative breaks or meditation (Uchenna, Ezekwe and Joanes, 2024). In the end, incorporating leisure activities into the workplace is a strategic tool that improves employee performance overall and their personal well-being. Businesses may foster a more positive work atmosphere where employees feel valued, engaged, and committed to their roles by giving them the option to engage in leisure activities.

Employee Productivity

Employee productivity is the speed at which workers finish projects and advance the objectives of the company in a predetermined amount of time. It is sometimes expressed as the amount of output produced for every unit of input—such as time, money, or effort. Anugwu and Okolocha, (2023) were on the view that the success of an organization depends on maximizing employee productivity in the cutthroat business environment of today. While poor productivity can result in higher expenses, inefficiencies, and decreased competitiveness, high productivity is linked to improved performance, profitability, and overall growth (Amanda and Akpana, 2023).

Employee productivity is influenced by a number of factors, such as individual motivation, work environment, management style, and job satisfaction (Grace, Leonard, Nnaemeka, 2023).

The importance of employee well-being and mental health is gaining attention in productivity research, as there is mounting data that suggests stress management and a positive work environment are critical to sustaining high production levels (Oladimeji, Abdulkareem and Ishola, 2023). For example, burnout can dramatically lower an employee's performance and engagement if they are overworked or under stress (Bob-Manuel, 2023). On the other hand, companies that support a positive work-life balance and provide wellness programs, such as leisure opportunities, frequently observe increases in the caliber and volume of work that their staff members generate.

Leisure activities and productivity are particularly related in high-pressure businesses like the oil and gas sector. Offering employees the chance to unwind and have fun can help them recharge in these types of settings, which improves their focus, creativity, and general performance (Igomu, 2023). Employees who engage in workplace leisure activities exhibit notable gains in their capacity to manage work-related stress, which has a direct impact on their productivity. In the same light, a study by Jibir, Abdu, and Buba, (2023) postulate that leisure activities improve workers' mental and physical well-being as well as their capacity to work effectively and accomplish organizational goals.

Workforce Commitment

The degree of devotion, allegiance, and attachment that workers have to their company and its objectives is referred to as their workforce commitment. It includes the psychological and emotional bond that workers have with the company, which affects both their inclination to stick around and how engaged they are in their work overall (Okereka and Abasili, 2024). The degree of devotion, allegiance, and attachment that workers have to their company and its objectives is referred to as their workforce commitment. It includes the psychological and emotional bond that workers have with the company, which affects both their inclination to stick around and how engaged they are in their work overall.

Chukwu and Essue, (2024), state that there are three primary categories of workforce commitment that are commonly identified: affective commitment, which involves emotional attachment, continuation commitment, which is based on the perceived cost of quitting, and normative commitment, which involves an obligation to stay. Positive outcomes like higher job satisfaction, lower attrition rates, and enhanced organizational performance are linked to high levels of staff engagement. A committed workforce plays a crucial role in the success of any organization. Employees who are strongly committed tend to exhibit higher levels of engagement, are more willing to go above and beyond in their roles, and are less likely to seek employment elsewhere. This translates into higher productivity, better collaboration, and more innovation within the organization (Inegbedion, 2022). Moreover, companies with dedicated staff frequently see decreased absenteeism, fewer employee turnover, and a stronger organizational culture—all of which support long-term stability and success (Anas and Isichei, 2024).

One factor that can enhance workforce commitment is the availability of employee support initiatives, such as leisure activities in the workplace. Popoola and Fagbola, (2023), are of the view that providing opportunities for relaxation, social interaction, and stress relief through leisure activities can foster a sense of belonging and improve commitment to work, which in turn strengthens employees' emotional attachment to the organization. In high-pressure sectors like oil and gas, where work demands are often strenuous, leisure activities can help mitigate job-related stress, enhancing affective commitment by promoting well-being and improving employee morale (Ekejiuba, Muritala, Abubakar and Sharma, 2023). Companies that invest in the well-being of their employees through such programs are likely to see an increase in loyalty and commitment, ultimately contributing to a more engaged and productive workforce.

Work-Life Balance

Work-life balance is the state in which a person's personal and professional obligations are balanced so that neither one takes precedence over the other. It is attained when workers are able to balance their personal and professional responsibilities without feeling overloaded by either (Epie, 2023). The concept has grown in significance in recent years as businesses have realized how important it is for workers to have a good work-life balance for their productivity, well-being, and job happiness. Employees who are adept at managing their time and energy are less likely to suffer from burnout, stress, or discontent, which improves their performance at work and in their personal lives (Omosebi, 2024).

Sustaining sound work-life equilibrium is crucial in cultivating staff engagement and loyalty towards the company. Workers are more likely to have health problems related to stress, lose motivation, and produce less work if they feel overworked or under constant pressure from their jobs (Nwambu, 2024). However, employees are more likely to feel appreciated and dedicated when companies provide flexible work schedules, remote work options, or recreational opportunities to enhance work-life

balance. These programs give people the chance to relax, pursue hobbies, and spend time with their families; all of which have a good impact on their mental and physical health (Tamunomiebi and Oyibo, 2020). It can be especially difficult to achieve work-life balance in high-stress industries like oil and gas. It may be challenging for employees to find time for their personal lives due to the demanding nature of their jobs, long hours, and physical hardship. Thus, it is essential to put work-life balance strategies into practice.

Companies can promote work-life balance by offering flexible schedules, stress management programs, and leisure activities that allow employees to recharge. Research shows that when employees feel their work and personal lives are well-balanced, they exhibit higher levels of productivity, engagement, and long-term organizational commitment (Akanji, Mordi and Ajonbadi, 2020). By fostering a culture of balance, organizations can enhance employee well-being and overall business performance. Beyond the well-being of the person, work-life balance is crucial because it directly affects corporate results, including staff retention, productivity, and general performance. Workers who successfully balance their personal and professional lives are typically more driven, committed, and focused on their work. On the other hand, people who have trouble staying balanced are more likely to experience stress, miss work, and be less productive (Nwagbara, 2020). Consequently, many organizations are adopting policies and practices aimed at improving work-life balance, including flexible working hours, telecommuting options, and wellness programs.

Workplace Environment

The physical, social, and psychological settings in which employees carry out their duties are referred to as the workplace environment. It includes a range of elements, including the physical work environment, company culture, communication styles, leadership philosophies, and the degree of assistance given to staff members (Arubayi, 2023). In order to promote employee engagement, productivity, and contentment, a positive work environment is essential. It directly affects workers' general well-being and productivity, as well as how they view their jobs and behave (Anekwe, Osarenoma and Ifeanyichukwu, 2024). A well-designed physical workspace can contribute significantly to employee productivity. Factors such as lighting, temperature, noise levels, and ergonomics play a crucial role in determining how comfortable and efficient employees are at their jobs. For example, studies (Chinonso, Eleje, Adeniyi, and Oluwayomi, (2024) have shown that access to natural light, proper ventilation, and comfortable furniture can reduce fatigue and increase concentration, leading to better performance.

Incorporating leisure into the workplace environment helps address the growing challenges of workplace stress and burnout. Ekerette and Sanusi, (2023) state that offering activities that allow employees to take breaks from their tasks, companies can reduce stress, foster creativity, and enhance problem-solving abilities. Research has shown that employees who participate in leisure activities such as physical exercise or mindfulness sessions tend to report higher levels of commitment and productivity,

lower rates of absenteeism, and improved mental health (Haruna, 2024). This is particularly important in high-stress industries like oil and gas, where the demands of the job can lead to exhaustion and decreased productivity if proper work-life balance is not maintained. It is a common saying all work without play makes Jack a dull worker. People need to ease off tension from work, hence a workplace environment that provides leisure activities to work will increase its productivity.

On the other hand, a badly constructed workstation that has uncomfortable chairs, loud noises, or insufficient illumination can cause stress and lower productivity. Olubiya, (2023), was of the view that a more balanced work atmosphere is also facilitated by the provision of leisure places, such as relaxation areas, gyms, and break rooms, which enable staff members to refuel and resume work with a fresh perspective. The social and psychological aspects of the workplace environment are equally important. A supportive organizational culture that fosters open communication, collaboration, and respect can significantly enhance employee motivation and commitment. When employees feel valued, respected, and part of a cohesive team, they are more likely to be engaged in their work and demonstrate higher levels of productivity (Okoroafor, Nwachukwu, Asamani, Ahmat, and Osubor, 2023). Another important factor in determining the nature of the workplace is leadership. Good leaders foster a culture of trust and motivation by giving clear instructions, encouragement, and providing leisure activities in the workplace. This inspires workers to put up their best effort. On the other hand, low leadership and a poisonous workplace marked by miscommunication, micromanagement, and a lack of encouragement can cause stress, high turnover rates, and employee unhappiness.

Types of Leisure Activities

Recreational and non-work-related activities that employees might partake in during breaks or specified relaxation periods are referred to as leisure activities in the workplace. Employees can refuel and rejuvenate through these activities, which enhances their general well-being, job commitment, and productivity (Ibrahim, 2024). Different types of leisure activities can cater to various interests and preferences, promoting a healthy work-life balance and contributing to a positive organizational culture.

Below are the key types of leisure activities commonly found in workplaces;

Physical Exercises

Sports, fitness, and other movement-based pastimes are examples of physical leisure activities that support workers' physical health and productivity. These activities could include walking clubs, yoga classes, gym memberships, or structured fitness programs at work (Umunakwe, 2021). Engaging in physical activities enhances mental clarity, lowers stress, and improves general health. These benefits can result in increased productivity and decreased absenteeism (Umunakwe, Ogbaa, and Amafilu, 2021). For example, a lot of businesses encourage their staff to be active by offering in-house workout centers or partnering with neighborhood gyms.

Social Activities

Social leisure activities promote interaction, teamwork, and relationship-building among employees. Examples of social activities include team-building exercises, company picnics, holiday parties, and lunch outings. These activities help break down barriers between employees, strengthen communication, and foster a sense of community within the organization (Adamou and Zoumari, 2024). Engaging in social activities can enhance employee morale, reduce work-related stress, and lead to stronger collaboration and loyalty within teams. Socializing in informal settings allows employees to relax and bond, leading to more cohesive working relationships.

Relaxation and Wellness Activities: Relaxation and wellness activities focus on mental and emotional well-being by promoting mindfulness, stress reduction, and self-care. Examples include meditation sessions, massages, spa treatments, and mindfulness programs. These activities help employees manage stress, improve mental clarity, and increase emotional resilience (Balogun, 2021). Given the demands and stress levels in industries such as oil and gas, incorporating wellness programs can help prevent burnout and improve employee satisfaction, thus contributing to a more productive and committed workforce.

Employees' Participation in Leisure Activities: Employees' participation in leisure activities within the workplace plays a significant role in improving overall well-being, job satisfaction, productivity, and workforce commitment. Workplace leisure activities provide a much-needed break from the stress and demands of work, enabling employees to recharge and return to their tasks with renewed energy and focus. This participation often leads to improved mental and physical health, strengthened interpersonal relationships, and increased motivation, all of which contribute to a more positive and productive work environment (Asiegbu, 2024). One of the key factors influencing employee participation in leisure activities is the organizational culture and leadership's support for such activities. Wang, Zhang and Shi, (2024) postulate that when leadership actively promotes and encourages participation, employees are more likely to feel comfortable engaging in these activities without fear of judgment or negative consequences on their work performance.

Additionally, offering a variety of leisure activities tailored to diverse interests and preferences can boost participation rates. Employees are more likely to engage in activities that resonate with their individual needs, such as fitness programs, mindfulness sessions, social events, or creative workshops (Kukoyi and Ijose, 2023). In providing inclusive and flexible leisure opportunities, organizations can ensure that more employees benefit from these activities, leading to higher engagement levels.

Moreover, research has shown that employees who regularly participate in leisure activities at work tend to have higher job satisfaction, better work-life balance, and increased commitment to their organization (Adamu and Bello, 2021). Participating in physical and social leisure activities reduces stress and helps employees build stronger connections with their colleagues, fostering a more collaborative and cohesive work environment. Onwuanyi and Nwodo, (2024) were on the view that cognitive and relaxation activities allow employees to manage work pressures more effectively,

promoting a sense of well-being that can translate into improved performance and loyalty to the organization. Therefore, organizations that prioritize leisure activities as part of the workplace wellness programs create a more engaged and motivated workforce, ultimately benefiting both employees and the company.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Model of Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) theory by Bakker and Demerouti (2007) which created the JD-R Model that offers a helpful framework for comprehending the ways in which employee dedication and productivity might be impacted by leisure activities. This theory is relevant to the present study because it emphasizes leisure activities in the workplace, such as social events, fitness programs, and creative workshops which will increase workers commitment and improve productivity. Organizations should address these needs by giving employees a sense of control over their work-life balance (autonomy), helping them develop new skills or maintain their health (competence), and fostering social connections with colleagues (relatedness). When employees engage in leisure activities that meet these intrinsic needs, they are more likely to experience higher levels of job satisfaction, improved productivity, and stronger organizational commitment. According to the JD-R model, every job has resources (such support, autonomy, and development (possibilities) as well as demands (like workload, pressure, and physical or emotional demands). Employee stress and burnout are more common in high-demanding industries like the oil and gas sector. Because they promote rest, relaxation, and recovery, leisure activities act as employment resources that assist employees in meeting these expectations. These activities promote employee engagement and performance, which in turn leads to higher productivity and stronger staff commitment by lowering stress and improving well-being.

Empirical Reviews

Mokaya and Gitari (2012) explored the effects of workplace recreation on employee performance. The research has shown that leisure activities, including physical exercise, recreational activities, and wellness programs, positively influence employee productivity. A study by Mokaya and Gitari (2012) highlights that employees who engage in regular leisure activities experience higher energy levels, better mental clarity, and improved focus, leading to enhanced productivity. This is particularly relevant in the oil and gas industry, where the high-stress work environment can lead to employee burnout and decreased performance. A study conducted in Port Harcourt by Blair, Blair, Howe, Pate, Rosenberg and Parker (1980) found that employees in oil and gas firms who participated in company-sponsored fitness and recreational programs reported improved concentration, reduced fatigue, and higher productivity levels compared to those who did not participate.

Similarly, Gellmers (2023) found that integrating physical activities into the workplace significantly reduced absenteeism and improved employee engagement in high-demand sectors such as oil and gas. Employees who regularly engaged in fitness programs or took breaks to engage in leisure activities

reported a reduction in stress and a significant improvement in their ability to manage complex tasks. This study highlights the potential for leisure activities to mitigate the negative effects of demanding productivity jobs. Data was collected for the research using a pre-tested, well-structured questionnaire administered to 320 respondents. Data collected were analyzed using SPSS version 20 and STATA version 12.0. Results of the analysis showed that the experience of the respondents is relatively high. Workers believe that the influence of leisure in the workplace can be reflected in job commitment and productivity. Personalized recommendations for leisure activities, but believe leisure in the workplace plays moderate role on the level of influence these personalized recommendations have on the decision to be committed in the organization. The results suggest that leisure activities in the workplace could impact on the productivity workers behavior in the organization.

In the hospitality industry, renowned for its high turnover rates, Mensah, Baah, Nutsugbodo and Ankor (2023) found that leisure activities significantly improved workforce commitment. Employees who participated in wellness programs were more likely to remain loyal to their employers, attributing the increased commitment to the perceived care and investment of their organizations in their well-being. This study's relevance to oil and gas lies in the high turnover and burnout rates common in both industries. The relationship between leisure activities and workforce commitment has been empirically supported by several studies. A study by Mokaya and Gitari (2012) found that employees who perceive their organization as supportive of work-life balance, including the provision of leisure activities, demonstrate stronger organizational commitment. This is because these employees feel valued by their employer, leading to increased loyalty and a greater willingness to invest effort into their work. In oil and gas firms in Rivers State, where long working hours and high-pressure environments are common, offering leisure activities can enhance employees' commitment by providing them with opportunities.

Wang, Chen, Zhang, and Wong (2025) explored how team leisure sports activities enhance the sustainability of construction workers' occupational commitment through the mediating effect of team cohesion, integrating perspectives from social psychology and organizational behavior. Data were collected from 509 Chinese construction workers using a structured questionnaire. The results revealed the following: (1) Four dimensions of team sports experience—social interaction quality, emotional engagement, team culture perception, and work pressure relief—positively affected workers' commitment to sustainability. (2) Team cohesion mediated the relationship between the team sports experience and sustainability. This study provides insights into career sustainability in the construction industry and highlights the importance of team cohesion in enhancing workers' professional commitment. The findings offer practical implications for optimizing team-building and human resource management strategies, with a focus on retaining employees in the construction industry.

Obiora-Okafo and Onodugo(2021) assess workplace recreation and employee well-being. The particular goals are to find out how physical fitness programs affect employee wellbeing at Nigerian

University Commission and how mental health programs affect employee wellbeing at Nigerian University Commission. The descriptive research method was used in this study. The study's population consisted of 748 Nigerian University Commission employees, with a sample size of 230 determined using the Taro Yamane formula. Simple percentage analysis was used to analyze the data, and Simple Linear regression was used to test all hypotheses at 0.05 alpha levels. Physical fitness programs have a substantial effect on employee wellbeing at Nigerian University Commission, and mental health programs have a large effect on employee wellbeing at Nigerian University Commission, according to the findings of the study. Physical fitness and mental health programs have a considerable favorable influence on employee wellness and performance, according to the study. It was suggested, among other things, that organizations should provide recreation facilities and activities that are of interest to employees, taking into account their various interests, gender, age, and other factors.

Gap in Literature

There exists methodological gap, the limited exploration of the specific types of leisure activities, variable gap, demographics gap, lack of Region-Specific Studies, and periodic gap. There is limited research on the present study. From the reviewed studies, the methodologies, variables, location and time are different from that of the present study. Therefore, this study sought to bridge these gaps.

METHODS

This study employed descriptive survey research design. The study adopted primary source of data and secondary source of information. The study employed random sampling probability technique in selecting 20 oil and gas firms in Rivers state, Nigeria. The target population were 203 staff of the selected 20 oil and gas firms in Rivers state, Nigeria. The hypotheses were tested with Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient on Statistical Packages for Social Science (SPSS version 27) at 5% level of significance.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Decision Rule:

Accept the null hypothesis (H_0) if calculated P-value is less than 0.05 ($p\text{-value} < 0.05$); otherwise accept the alternate hypothesis (H_a).

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis One

H_{01} : There is no significant relationship between the availability of workplace leisure activities and employee productivity in oil and gas firms in Rivers State.

H_{a1} : There is significant relationship between the availability of workplace leisure activities and employee productivity in oil and gas firms in Rivers State.

Table 1: Relationship between the availability of workplace leisure activities and employee productivity in oil and gas firms in Rivers State, Nigeria.

		Workplace leisure Activities	Employee productivity
Workplace leisure Activities	Pearson correlation	1	.882**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001
	N	203	203
Employee productivity	Pearson correlation	.882**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	
	N	203	203

Source: SPSS version 27 Outputs.

Discussion of Findings

Table 1. Shows that there is a significant relationship between the availability of workplace leisure activities and employee productivity in oil and gas firms in Rivers state Nigeria.

, with $r = 0.882$ $n = 203$ and p value of 0.001 ($p < 0.05$). Therefore, the study accepted the alternate hypothesis and concluded that there is a significant positive relationship between the availability of workplace leisure activities and employee productivity in oil and gas firms in Rivers state Nigeria. This implies that the availability of workplace leisure activities can improve and increase employee productivity in oil and gas firms in Rivers state Nigeria leading to more revenue generation in the oil and gas sector.

Hypothesis Two

H_{02} : There is no significant relationship between Leisure activities and workforce commitment in oil and gas firms in Rivers state, Nigeria.

H_a : There is a significant relationship between workplace Leisure activities and workforce commitment in oil and gas firms in Rivers state, Nigeria.

Table 2: Relationship between workplace Leisureactivities and workforce commitment in oil and gas firms in Rivers state, Nigeria.

		Workplace leisure Activities	Workforce Commitment
	Pearson correlation	1	.801**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
Workplace leisure Activities	N	203	203
	Pearson correlation	.801**	1
Workforce Commitment	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	203	203

Source: SPSS version 27 Outputs.

Discussion of Findings

Table 2 shows that there is a positive significant relationship between workplace Leisure activities and workforce commitment in oil and gas firms in Rivers state, Nigeria, with $r = 0.801$, $n = 203$ and p value of 0.000 ($p < 0.05$). Therefore, the study accepted the alternate hypothesis and concluded that there is a positive significant relationship between workplace Leisure activities and workforce commitment in oil and gas firms in Rivers state, Nigeria. This implies that the Influence of workplace Leisure Activities on Workforce Commitment in Oil and Gas Firms in Rivers State, Nigeria, can significantly enhance workforce commitment by improving well-being satisfaction, employee welfare, and job satisfaction, leading to a more healthy working relationship and motivated workforce.

Conclusion

The study found that employee productivity at oil and gas firms in Rivers State, Nigeria, is positively correlated with workplace leisure activities in a statistically significant way. The study's conclusion is that, by increasing productivity and fostering employee job satisfaction, the provision of leisure activities at work can have a major positive impact on the long-term workforce commitment of oil and gas companies in River State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

In light of the research's conclusions and gaps, the following suggestions are offered to enhance the way leisure activities are implemented and how successful they are in raising worker's commitment and productivity in Nigerian oil and gas firms located in Rivers State:

1. Encourage Work-Life Balance Initiatives: Oil and gas companies should incorporate recreational activities into larger work-life balance programs. Leisure programs can enhance physical and social

aspects of life by providing access to mental health resources, paid time off for wellness activities, and flexible work schedules.

2. Integrate Tailored and Structured Recreation Programs: Oil and gas companies should put in place well-planned, structured recreational programs that meet the various demands of their staff. Fitness courses, leisure sports, and team-building activities as a few examples of the physical, social, and creative activities that these programs ought to provide.

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